

CAN WE TALK ABOUT IT? THE DIFFICULTY OF DISCUSSING TRANSGENDERISM

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INTRODUCTION

When pressing and controversial societal questions arise, open discussion offers an opportunity to exchange opposing views, to ask one's interlocutor to justify their position, and to be at liberty to question that position's premises, underlying evidence, or the internal consistency of their argument. This view of discussion reflects much that is held dear in liberal philosophy; but even the most historically influential theorists of liberalism and advocates of free speech have recognised the importance of setting boundaries (legal and/or social) to what can and should legitimately be said. Thus, JS Mill argued that "all that makes existence valuable to anyone depends on the enforcement of restraints upon the actions of other people. Some rules of conduct, therefore, must be imposed—by law in the first place, and by opinion on many things which are not fit subjects for the operation of law".² The establishment of such boundaries is often referred to as the "harm principle" following Mill's view that the only justification for the curtailment of liberty is to prevent harm to others. For those who subscribe to the harm principle, the questions of what constitutes harm, what is a fit subject for the operation of law (rather than informal social censure), and how this balance should be policed, are much debated – whilst others hold that the harm principle itself is overly-restrictive when applied to speech, and others still find the harm principle insufficiently restrictive, appealing to alternative notions such as offence.³

Today, the most prominent debate where these considerations apply is that surrounding transgender identity. In the context of this debate, it is an increasingly widely held view in Western Europe and North America that manifestations of beliefs critical of transgenderism are in themselves harmful and

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² John Stuart Mill, *On Liberty*, (Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing, 1978), 5.

³ Feinberg, J., *Harm to Others: The Moral Limits of the Criminal Law* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1984).

not worthy of legal protection. Indeed, a stronger version of this view has also gained prominence, which holds that so-called “gender-critical” *beliefs in themselves* should not be protected on the basis that such beliefs would *necessarily* lead to external conduct that would violate the dignity and conflict with the fundamental rights of others; this was notably the view propounded by the UK employment tribunals in two recent decisions: *Forstater v CGD Europe* and *Mackereth v DWP*.⁴ This sort of reasoning raises questions about the validity of a distinction between an absolute *forum internum* and a qualified *forum externum* in the architecture of the right to freedom of belief or religion: can clear lines be drawn between the holding of a belief, its manifestation, and the conditions of its manifestation?⁵ For the purposes of the present discussion, I will largely leave this level of analysis aside and focus on what these two cases can tell us about the seeming intractability of disagreement between advocates of transgender rights and advocates of the right to freedom of religion and belief today. My view is this: the debate over transgenderism is not only (or even primarily) about competing definitions of what it means to be a man or a woman. To a large extent, the vitriol surrounding this debate must be understood on a meta-conceptual level. What separates opponents is their differing views on what can legitimately be discussed in a pluralistic society, when speech constitutes a harm, and whether certain beliefs in themselves are tolerable if such beliefs undermine certain persons’ self-understandings.

BELIEFS NOT WORTHY OF RESPECT?

In both *Forstater v CGD Europe* and *Mackereth v DWP*, claims were brought to the Employment tribunal under the Equality Act 2010 (EqA), which prohibits four basic forms of discrimination (direct, indirect, harassment and victimisation) on the basis of nine protected characteristics (Age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage or civil partnership [in employment only], pregnancy and maternity, race, religion or belief, sex, sexual orientation) in contexts which include employment and the provision of goods and services.

In the case of *Mackereth v DWP*, the claimant was a doctor who, as a Christian, held the following beliefs or lack of belief:

⁴ *Hurford v Farmor’s School* is also a relevant case here, but I leave it aside for the purposes of my present discussion.

⁵ On this question, Rebecca Roberts argues that, in the content of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), the *forum internum* and *forum externum* aspects of art. 9 are interrelated and should be understood on a conceptual continuum ranging from the *forum internum* to the *forum externum* because the former is always relevant, to some degree, in Article 9 complaints. See: Roberts, C. K., 2020. *Reconceptualising the Place of the Forum Internum and Forum Externum in Article 9 of the European Convention on Human Rights*, 2020. PhD thesis, University of Bristol.

“(a) in the truth of Genesis 1:27, that a person cannot change their sex/gender at will and attempting to do so is pointless, self-destructive and sinful;

(b) a lack of belief in “Transgenderism” and “gender fluidity”, such that he does not believe (i) a person can change sex/gender, (ii) that “impersonating” the opposite sex may be beneficial for a person’s welfare, or (iii) that society should accommodate/encourage such “impersonation”;

(c) a belief that it would be irresponsible and dishonest for a health professional to accommodate/encourage a patient’s “impersonation” of the opposite sex.”⁶

The Claimant, Dr. Mackereth, held that because of these beliefs he would not be able to address transgender service users by their chosen pronouns, a position contrary to his employer’s policy. Dr. Mackereth’s claim to the tribunal was that he had suffered less favourable treatment and discrimination because of his beliefs, in that pressure had been put on him to renounce his beliefs, he had been suspended from work, and he had been summarily dismissed. The tribunal found against the claimant, notably on the basis that his particular beliefs regarding transgenderism were incompatible with human dignity and were in conflict with the fundamental rights of transgender individuals, and thus did not meet all of the so-called *Grainger* criteria.⁷ *Grainger* holds that in order to qualify as a “philosophical belief” under section 10 EqA a belief must (i) be genuinely held; (ii) be a belief and not an opinion or viewpoint based on the present state of information available; (iii) be a belief as to a weighty and substantial aspect of human life and behaviour; (iv) attain a certain level of cogency, seriousness, cohesion and importance; and (v) be worthy of respect in a democratic society, not be incompatible with human dignity, and not conflict with the fundamental rights of others. More specifically, the tribunal held that Dr. Mackereth’s lack of belief in “Transgenderism” and “gender fluidity”, such that he did not believe that “impersonating” the opposite sex may be beneficial for a person’s welfare (b.ii) and that society should accommodate/encourage such “impersonation (b.iii) did not meet *Grainger* ii, iii, and iv; and that none of his beliefs satisfied *Grainger* (v). The claimant’s views were not, therefore, protected as religious or philosophical beliefs under the Equality Act.

Importantly, the tribunal’s judgment was not limited to a consideration of Dr. Mackereth’s actions but considered his *beliefs in themselves* to be “likely to cause offence and have the effect of violating a transgender person’s dignity or

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⁷ *Grainger plc v Nicholson* [2010] ICR 360, para 24. These criteria have been adopted in the ECHR Code of Practice for employment at paragraph 2.59. Whilst tribunals are required to take the code of practice into account, they are not bound by it. According to *Harron v Chief Constable of Dorset Police* [2016] IRLR 481, EAT, para 34: The threshold for establishing the *Grainger* criteria should not be set “too high”.

creating a proscribed environment, or subjecting a transgender person to less favourable treatment. They [the beliefs] may also have breached the GDA [sic. GRA (Gender Recognition Act 2004)].”⁸

The case of *Forstater v CGD Europe* presents a similar slippage between belief and action on behalf of the tribunal. Ms Forstater was employed as a consultant for CGD Europe, a development think tank. During the time of her employment, she had written several messages on her private Twitter account reflecting her view that:

(a) “sex” is a material reality which should not be conflated with “gender” or “gender identity”;

(b) being female is an immutable biological fact, not a feeling or an identity;

(c) that sex matters and that it is important to be able to talk about and take action against the discrimination, violence and oppression that still affect women and girls because they were born female.

After receiving complaints from colleagues, who considered that she was expressing transphobic opinions, Ms. Forstater’s employer conducted an investigation and later decided not to renew her contract. In this case, the claimant alleged discrimination on the basis of her gender critical philosophical beliefs when her contract was not renewed. Again, the tribunal found against the claimant on the basis that Ms. Forstater’s beliefs were not protected under the Equality Act 2010 as her views were “absolutist in nature, incompatible with human dignity and fundamental rights of others [and thus] not worthy of respect in a democratic society”.⁹ Importantly, in terms more explicit than in the Mackereth case, the judge in *Forstater* motivated his decision on the basis of the following consideration:

“I draw a distinction between belief and separate action based on the belief that may constitute harassment. However, if part of the belief necessarily will result in the violation of the dignity of others, that is a component of the belief, rather than something separate, and will be relevant to determining whether the belief is a protected philosophical belief. While the Claimant will as a matter of courtesy use preferred pronouns she will not as part of her belief ever accept that a trans woman is a woman or a trans man a man, however hurtful it is to others.”¹⁰

We may assume that the judge’s appeal to action here is intended to serve as a standard for determining whether Ms. Forstater’s belief falls foul of the *Grainger* (v) threshold. Admittedly, it is not obvious how this determination

⁸ Mackereth ET 198.

⁹ Forstater, 84.

¹⁰ Forstater, 88, my emphasis.

should be made.¹¹ James Hurford has argued that Grainger (v) is badly worded as it conflates the notion of respect with that of toleration – the former implying too high a bar given that the state is meant to act as a neutral arbiter¹². Russell Sandberg has also criticised the Grainger criteria on the basis that their inconsistent application has contributed to a growing confusion as to the definitional boundaries of a belief: “Employment Tribunals have considered the tests to be met in cases concerning beliefs in spiritualism and psychic powers, anti-fox hunting beliefs, beliefs in the virtue of public service broadcasting, and Humanist beliefs. In contrast, other Employment Tribunals have concluded that the tests have not been met in cases concerning Marxist/Trotskyite beliefs held by trade union members, beliefs in conspiracy theories regarding 9/11, and a belief that belief that a Poppy should be worn during the week prior to Remembrance Sunday”.¹³

Further to these more general points, two ambiguous moves are made in the tribunal’s statement regarding Forstater. First, in terms similar to, but more explicit than in the Mackereth case, the tribunal acknowledges a distinction between holding and manifesting a belief - whilst at the same time collapsing the efficacy of that distinction by qualifying the right to hold a belief on the hypothesis that such a belief is associated, through a form of necessary causation, with a corollary action (even if no specific instance of such action has been demonstrated to occur). Second, the tribunal states that even if the claimant does modify her external behavior regarding the use of pronouns, she remains at fault because she will not *accept* that a trans woman is a woman. To use preferred pronouns out of courtesy is not sufficient; the action must be supported by proper belief. But how is such a belief to be verified given that the external manifestation is itself insufficient? Andrew Hambler has described this reasoning as “an approach fraught with danger. The implication is that a belief, before it is even expressed, is beyond the pale owing to its capacity to ‘violate the dignity of others’ (that is, cause offense). Indeed, the judge seems to go so

¹¹ Sandberg 2018: Following Grainger the five requirements have taken on an elevated importance. Employment Tribunal Chairs have subsequently applied these requirements as if they were a statutory test and have forgotten the warning in Williamson that these should be ‘minimum’ and ‘modest’ requirements.⁶¹ They have interpreted the tests in different ways to reach inconsistent and arbitrary decisions. Employment Tribunals have considered the tests to be met in cases concerning beliefs in spiritualism and psychic powers,⁶² anti-fox hunting beliefs,⁶³ beliefs in the virtue of public service broadcasting,⁶⁴ and Humanist beliefs.⁶⁵ In contrast, other Employment Tribunals have concluded that the tests have not been met in cases concerning Marxist / Trotskyite beliefs held by trade union members,⁶⁶ beliefs in conspiracy theories regarding 9/11,⁶⁷ and a belief that belief that a Poppy should be worn during the week prior to Remembrance Sunday.⁶⁸ Drawing any points of principle out of this case law is difficult, to say the least.⁶⁹

¹² Hurford, J. E., “Worthy of Respect in a Democratic Society? Forstater and the Expression of Controversial Beliefs,” *Judicial Review* 26, no. 4. (2021): 277-290.

¹³ Sandberg, R., “Clarifying the definition of religion under English law: The need for a universal definition,” *Ecclesiastical Law Journal*, 20, no. 2, (2018): 132-157.

far as to suggest that because dignity *will be* violated then that fact in itself operates to demonstrate that a belief rather than ‘an action based on belief’ is in play.”¹⁴ Robert Wintemute advances a similar argument.¹⁵ However, Cowan and Morris disagree with this critique on the basis that “the Tribunal took the view that there was unequivocal evidence, from Ms. Forstater herself, of previous conduct arising from her beliefs, and an intention to act on these beliefs in the same way going forward. Having considered all the factual evidence, the Tribunal concluded that Ms. Forstater’s beliefs *necessarily* led to conduct that violated dignity, in conflict with the fundamental rights of others, and which was not worthy of respect in a democratic society. Therefore, it found those views not worthy of protection under the EqA”.¹⁶ Yet, it is still the case that this is an inductive leap in the tribunal’s logic, from previous conduct to necessary future conduct. 1 As Hambler points out, in Mackereth, the judge added a confusing postscript which stated that the tribunal had no doubt of the claimant’s ‘entitlement to hold [his] beliefs’ but that what the case concerned was ‘whether he was entitled to manifest those beliefs in the circumstances that applied’: “How this postscript can be reconciled with the earlier part of the judgment which declared the claimant’s actual beliefs to be incompatible with human dignity and the rights of others is unclear”.¹⁷

Subsequent to these first instance decisions, the Employment Appeal Tribunal overturned the determination in Ms. Forester’s case, finding that her views were indeed worthy of respect in a democratic society and that she had been unfairly discriminated against. Dr. Mackereth also lodged an appeal; in this instance the tribunal dismissed the appeal, although, citing Forstater, the EAT recognised that the ET had erred in its approach to defining religion and belief as a protected characteristic (and specifically in its application of the Grainger criteria).¹⁸

THE ABSENCE OF COMMON GROUND

Confusions in the judges’ written rulings aside, the logic hinted at in these two cases is indicative of at least one key reason why the societal debate concerning transgenderism is so brittle. For those skeptical of the notion that gender is a

¹⁴ Hambler, A., “Beliefs Unworthy of Respect in a Democratic Society: A View from the Employment Tribunal,” *Ecclesiastical Law Journal* 22, no. 2, (2020): 234-241. My emphasis.

¹⁵ Wintemute, R., “Belief vs. action in Ladele, Ngole and Forstater,” *Industrial Law Journal* 50, no.1, (2021): 104-117.

¹⁶ Cowan, S., & Morris, S., “Should ‘Gender Critical’ Views about Trans People Be Protected as Philosophical Beliefs in the Workplace? Lessons for the Future from Forstater, Mackereth and Higgs,” *Industrial Law Journal* 51, no. 1, (2022): 1-37.

¹⁷ Hambler, op. cit.

¹⁸ Appeal, 58.

matter for autonomous self-identification (neither determined by biological sex nor tied to sexual orientation), the freedom to hold and manifest their beliefs is both conceived of as a matter of conscience and as a useful deliberative practice necessary to assess the truthfulness of claims which carry grave social and political consequence. Inherent to their position is the idea that the meaning of the claim “to be trans-gender” is not settled, that such a proposition may refer to an objective reality other than that which a self-identified trans-gender person attributes to it, and that the belief in transgenderism may not only be empirically false (a “fiction” to use Kathleen Stock’s term), but that the legal recognition of this belief as true may cause harm to persons, notably biologically-born women and girls. For example, *Transgender Trend*, a UK organisation calling for evidence-based treatment of children with gender dysphoria and the end to teaching the concept of ‘gender identity’ as fact in schools, has raised concerns that the recent increase of girls who develop gender dysphoria at or after puberty is attributable to poor body image and that transgender affirmation only reinforces this problem.¹⁹ In sum, those of this disposition hold that to debate what it means to be trans is a legitimate line of inquiry; further, they hold that it is a morally necessary line of inquiry.

On the other hand, many proponents of transgenderism hold that the very belief in the biological model of sex difference is harmful on the basis that it threatens “the existence and validity of transgender and nonbinary people, and the right of trans and nonbinary people to identify their own genders and sexualities. [As such, transgenderism falls] within the range of [...] indisputable topics.”²⁰ Although the extent and verifiability of such harms may be disputed, proponents of transgenderism insist that a situated perspective is necessary to appreciate their depth of force: “What seems mundane to people who aren’t trans can mean everything to the person being impacted. A mere moment may constitute that final layer of injustice for a trans person who finds themselves no longer able to resist.”²¹ For people of this disposition, it is both intellectually illegitimate and morally harmful to debate what it means to be trans.

These two positions point to a meta-disagreement regarding the legitimacy of having a debate about transgenderism, which cannot be resolved as this would require mobilizing substantive concepts from within the debate, which one party or another dismisses axiomatically. In his examination of the nature of modern moral disagreement in *After Virtue*, Alisdair MacInyre made precisely this observation, that “the most striking feature of contemporary moral utterance is that so much of it is used to express disagreements; and that the

¹⁹ Written evidence submitted by Transgender Trend to Parliament (MISS0046).

²⁰ Joint Statement of Minorities and Philosophy and Minorities and Philosophy International, 2019.

²¹ Mermaids UK. <https://mermaidsuk.org.uk/news/trans-rights-are-not-up-for-debate/>.

most striking feature of the debates in which these disagreements are expressed in their interminable character. [Not just that they go on and on] but also that they apparently can find no terminus”.²² Intractable debates, on MacIntyre’s account, have three salient characteristics, which each apply to the transgender debate: the conceptual incommensurability of the rival arguments; the impersonal mode of such arguments which severs the link between the context of utterance and the force of the reason-giving: rival claims are to be evaluated independently of the preferences and attitudes of speaker and hearer; and the historical decontextualisation of rival arguments which hides how wide and heterogeneous the variety of moral sources is from which we have inherited our beliefs.

The transgender debate in its current form is intractable not because of empirical or moral disagreements between opponents. Indeed, if this were the case, we could resolve the debate through scientific inquiry or moral deliberation - or at least identify the conditions under which such a resolution would obtain. Rather, what prevents the transgender debate from being conducted through a civil exchange of ideas progressing towards more well-defined concepts and a narrower mutual understanding of the terms of disagreement is that there is “no rational way of securing moral agreement” between the two sides.

Is there way out of this intractable debate? A modest hopefulness might be found in the distinction we can make between ‘talking together’ and ‘living together’. Like much modern moral disagreement, the debate over transgenderism happens in an amorphous space between groups who share little or no common life together. Thus, for both sides, the importance of abstract ideas is elevated (either to be sanctified or reviled) but the actual lived humanity of persons who hold ideals, make moral commitments, have a sense of self-identity, is often lost. This phenomenon is accentuated on digital platforms where one’s interlocutors can appear as totally disembodied and where all one might “see” of the other person is the narrow set of beliefs or opinions with which one disagrees. The fact that a person also lives in a certain place to which they contribute through their daily work, has friends and family to whom they are committed, feels joy, fear, and suffering just as oneself does – these crucial details which make a person are far too easy to forget or ignore when we do not live alongside one another on a daily basis and share in both the happy and painful minutiae of life. MacIntyre’s focus on personalisation and community points to the preeminence of shared living over the Cartesian/Liberal focus on the depersonalised exchange of ideas.

The way in which we tend to think about the conduct of politics incites us to consider large-scale, public debates to be more important and more worthy

²² MacIntyre, A., *After virtue*. (A&C Black, 2013). 7.

than local discussions and parochial concerns. We want to speak or publish on platforms that will reach across the world, with little consideration for whether our immediate neighbors will ever hear or be interested in what we have to say; local public offices are seen as stepping-stones for national ambitions. And so often we are frustrated because the scope of our works does not reach these lofty goals – without ever considering whether they were worthy goals to begin with. Perhaps this hubristic, depersonalised approach to politics is also to blame for our incapacity to have a genuine and fruitful exchange of ideas with those whose views we contest. An alternative vision holds that a deep and prolonged experience of living together as a community is a necessary prior condition to a meaningful dialogue on difficult questions. Investing oneself in one’s local community through service, getting to know those with whom we work and those near to whom we live, listening to and sharing stories rather than opinions, waiting for empathy to grow organically through time spent together: all these modest (yet demanding) acts are good in themselves, but also instrumentally good because they gradually ease us into a state of mutual recognition where we can engage in a discussion of ideas on divisive questions; a discussion which we have not because of the ideas themselves, but because of a common commitment to each other and to the lives which we share in a real and tangible way.

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